

ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: This article examines the impact of artificial intelligence, which in the modern conditions of dynamic market development and rapid growth of the competitive environment, the issue of quality management has become key to the successful functioning of enterprises. The abstract is devoted to the organizational and economic aspects of quality management, considering the principles, methods and mechanisms that allow you to effectively integrate quality management systems into the organization's strategy. Analyzes the role of organizational structures and processes in ensuring a high level of quality of products and services using artificial intelligence. Particular attention is paid to the issues of adapting organizational models to the requirements of quality standards, such as ISO 9001, and the influence of economic factors on management decision-making.

Key words: artificial intelligence, quality, competitiveness, economic indicators of quality, aspects of quality, quality assurance process, quality management.

Today, artificial intelligence is increasingly used in the economic and industrial activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The market economy of Uzbekistan is characterized by competition between market participants and objects. Competition is a rivalry between individuals or business entities that seek to achieve the same goals in a certain area of activity.

Closely related to competition is the concept of competitiveness, which means the ability to successfully withstand rivalry. This term is applied to both goods and services, and to enterprises and organizations. The competitiveness of a product is its relative characteristic, reflecting the difference between this product and the products of competitors. This difference can be assessed both by the degree of satisfaction of the same social need, and by the costs of this satisfaction. Costs include the price that the consumer pays, as well as all expenses associated with the acquisition and use of the product.

In addition, artificial intelligence (AI) can greatly improve the competitiveness of products through data analysis, process automation, and personalization of offerings. Here are some ways in which AI can impact competitiveness: Consumer Preference Analysis: AI can

process large amounts of data on customer purchases, preferences, and behavior, allowing companies to better understand their needs and tailor their products and marketing accordingly.

- Price Optimization: Machine learning algorithms can analyze market prices in real time, allowing companies to respond flexibly to changes and offer competitive prices.
- Demand Forecasting: AI can help forecast consumer demand, which can improve inventory management and minimize overstocking.
- Personalized Marketing: AI can be used to create personalized advertising offers, which increases the likelihood of purchase and improves the customer experience.
- Process automation: Implementing AI into manufacturing processes can lead to increased efficiency and reduced costs, which will also have a positive impact on the competitiveness of the product.

Thus, the competitiveness of a product is a multifaceted concept that includes both traditional indicators and modern technologies, such as artificial intelligence, which can significantly improve market positions.

The competitiveness of a product can be characterized by three main groups of indicators:

Fig. 1. Groups of indicators of product quality and competitiveness.

Methods for assessing product quality include: differential and complex. Differential methodThe method of assessing product quality is based on the use of individual indicators. The differential method is carried out by comparing the quality indicators of the type of product being assessed with the corresponding base indicators, i.e. the quality indicator of the product being assessed P_i is compared with the quality indicator of the base sample P_{ibase} .

$$K_i = P_i / P_{ibase}, (1)$$

where P_i - is the numerical value of the 1st quality indicator of the assessed product;

P_{ibase} - is the numerical value of the 1st quality indicator of the base sample.

This formula is used when an increase in the absolute value of a quality indicator corresponds to an improvement in product quality (power, service life, productivity, efficiency, etc.).

$$K_i = P_i \text{ base} / P_i, (2)$$

According to this formula, the relative quality indicator is determined when an increase in the absolute value of the indicator corresponds to a deterioration in the quality of the product.

The complex evaluation method is used on the basis of a complex quality indicator. The quality level according to this method is determined by the ratio of the generalized quality indicator of the evaluated product Q_w . to the generalized indicator of the base sample, Q_{base} , i.e.

$$K = Q_w / Q_{\text{base}} (3)$$

The whole complexity of the assessment by the complex method lies in the objective finding of the generalized indicator. This method helps to obtain competitive products most effectively.

Table 1. Quality indicator of a competitive product as assessed by AI

Differential method	K_i	R_i	$R_i \text{ base}$
<i>qualities of the assessed species</i>	+	+	+
<i>quality indicator of the evaluated product</i>	+	+	+
<i>Competitiveness of the manufacturer</i>	High competitiveness index	Average competitiveness index	High level

The study of the competitiveness of goods is important for manufacturing enterprises, since market relations do not allow them to occupy a stable position in the market for a long time, relying in their production and sales strategy only on the indicators of the competitiveness of the goods, i.e. without taking into account the costs of its production and sale. The competitiveness of a manufacturer is its ability to maintain and expand sales markets due to targeted activities both in relation to the quality characteristics of the products and in relation to competing manufacturers. All decisions related to entering new sales markets, reorganization of the organizational structure, modification and development of new types of products, changes in the volume of their output, replacement of fixed production assets, changes in business ties and marketing policy are subordinated to ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise.

The categories of "product competitiveness" and "producer competitiveness" are interdependent. An enterprise cannot be competitive if its product has no market. However, product competitiveness is not a decisive factor in enterprise competitiveness. In some cases, product competitiveness is ensured by selling it at dumping prices that do not compensate for the costs of its production and distribution (which, over a sufficiently long period of time, can lead to the bankruptcy of the manufacturer).

While being closely interconnected, the categories of competitiveness of goods and enterprises also have significant differences:

Fig. 2. Categories of competitiveness of goods and enterprises

In its structure, the competitiveness of an enterprise is much more complex than the competitiveness of products, since the object of its application is the entire production and economic activity of the enterprise.

The competitiveness of an enterprise is determined by the action of a complex of factors of the external and internal environment of its life. The factors of the external environment may include:

- the level of government regulation and development of the economy of the country of residence (taxation, credit and financial and banking system, legislative support for business, system of foreign economic relations, etc.);
- - communication system;
- - organization of input material flows;
- - factors determining product consumption (market capacity, consumer requirements for product quality, etc.);

Internal environmental factorsThe enterprises are characterized by the following internal production indicators:

- technical level of production (condition and level of utilization of production capacities);
- technology;
- organization of production and management;
- a system of demand generation and stimulation, etc.

The enterprise's ability to influence environmental factors is limited, since they act objectively in relation to the enterprise. Real and immediate opportunities for regulating the enterprise's competitiveness are related to the sphere of internal environmental factors, but the enterprise can influence these factors with varying intensity. Serious capital investments and a long payback period require changes in the technical and technological conditions of the enterprise's operation. The most mobile and amenable to effective regulation without significant capital investments are the factors of the organization of production and sales management, and it is in this sphere that

real ways of increasing the enterprise's competitiveness are found. The decisive lever in this case is the product quality management system implemented by the enterprise.

The competitiveness of an enterprise can be assessed by comparing specific positions of several enterprises in the same market according to such parameters as: ability to adapt to changing competitive conditions, technology, equipment resolution, knowledge and practical experience of personnel, management system, marketing policy, image and communications. We are talking about a set of intellectual, technical and technological and organizational and economic characteristics that determine the success of an enterprise in the market.

The problem of quality and increasing competitiveness is becoming key for Russian enterprises, contributing to the obvious growth of interest in strategic business issues and in the problem of quality, as well as in approaches and methods for solving them, expressed in various forms:

- - concentration of efforts of a wide range of companies on establishing the production of products that are competitive in their characteristics;
- - studying the experience of Western companies that supply products to the world market that are superior in their parameters to domestic ones, with the aim of possibly using them at their own enterprise;
- - intensification of activities to develop and implement a product quality management system that meets the requirements of international standards (in economically developed countries, these systems are not only a source of competitive advantages, but also a mandatory infrastructural basis for effective interaction between companies in the context of a rapidly deepening division of labor);
- - the gradual awareness by Russian managers of the need to master a new philosophy of quality and, on its basis, the formation in companies of an organizational culture that is fundamentally new for domestic practice.

Solving the quality problem is an integral element of the development strategy of modern companies, therefore, the implementation of a product quality management system should begin with determining the place of this system in the overall strategy of the company.

Since the activity of forming a product quality management system by implementing international standards and principles of TQM (total quality management) is aimed at improving the quality and competitiveness of the company's products (services), all processes related to this activity should begin with an analysis of the needs and expectations of consumers of these products (services). Therefore, the company must first of all determine a marketing strategy that will reflect the interests and characteristics of consumers and the nature of the competitive advantages of its products (services), due to which it expects to achieve success.

In accordance with the marketing strategy, the company's assets and its technological potential must be developed, therefore a technical development strategy is necessary.

The quality of products and their competitiveness significantly depend on the quality and mode of supply of materials and components, therefore a strategy for the company's interaction with their suppliers is necessary.

The creation and practical use of artificial intelligence and product quality management systems depend on people, their qualifications and ability to constantly learn and improve their knowledge and skills, and their real involvement in activities to solve the quality problem. This necessitates an effective personnel management strategy.

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